

VISCOSITY OF SUPERSATURATED SOLUTIONS OF SOME IONIC CRYSTALS

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Measurements of viscosity of supersaturated solutions of KCl, KBr, KI, K_2SO_4 , $K_2Cr_2O_7$, $KClO_4$, NH_4Cl , NH_4Br and $Ba(NO_3)_2$ have been conducted by the method of Scarpa, modified by Taimni. It has been shown that η - T curve for substances like KCl, KBr, KI and K_2SO_4 , temperature coefficient of solubility of which is constant, is a straight line and for others such a proportionality is not obtained.

Miers and Issac (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 413, et seq) have shown that solutions saturated at a temperature T_s , if cooled, give rise to spontaneous crystallisation at a lower temperature T_0 , definite for each substance. In extending this work to a few ionic crystals, Srikantan (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 627) has shown that $T_s - T_0$, the limit of supersaturation, is constant for those substances temperature coefficient of solubility of which is constant throughout the range; substances like NH_4Cl , $KClO_4$, KNO_3 have different values for $T_s - T_0$ at different temperature regions, depending on the solubility coefficient at each range. In the absence of viscosity data of supersaturated solutions, Srikantan (*ibid.*, 1952, 29, 674) has further shown in a semiquantitative way, that

$$(T_s - T_0) (\eta_s - \eta_0) = K,$$

where η_s and η_0 are the viscosity of supersaturated solutions at T_s and T_0 respectively. Since data on the viscosity of supersaturated solutions were not available (except by Chatterji and Ramgopal, *ibid.*, 1947, 24, 455) the author had taken the viscosities of concentrated solutions only, thus leading to tentative conclusions. An attempt has been made herein to measure the viscosity of supersaturated solutions of a few ionic crystals and the results have been used to verify the above equation.

Saturated solutions at temperature T_s were cooled through the range $T_s - T_c$, characteristic of each substance, and the viscosity in the range $T_s - T_c$ was measured at different temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The viscosity measurements were made by means of an apparatus devised by Scarpa (*Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 261*) and used by Farrow (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347). Certain modifications were introduced to the above method by Taimni (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 604) to prevent the inoculation of the supersaturated solutions with germ crystals carried by dust particles. Further modifications (indicated in Fig. 1) were carried out resulting in greater reproducibility of the results.

The method consists in measuring the time t_1 taken in drawing up, by suction, a sufficient quantity of solution to fill a bulb at the top of a capillary tube, and the time t_2 which this volume of the solution takes in flowing out through the capillary tube

* The paper has been translated from Italian by Mr. G. Martirosi, Italian Chamber of Commerce, Madras-1.

under the action of gravity. Given constant conditions, the viscosity (η) of any liquid, according to Scarpa, is proportional to the expression,

$$\frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2} \quad \text{or} \quad \eta = K \times \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2},$$

where K is a constant which can be determined by calibrating the viscometer with water. So it is not necessary to measure the dimensions of the viscometer. It has been found that K varies slightly with increase in temperature (Table I).

TABLE I

Pressure (cm.) ...	19	19	25	25
Temp. ...	40°	50°	40°	50°
$K \times 10^3$...	57.69	56.85	75.51	74.66

However, the great advantage of this method over the ordinary method lies in the fact that it is not necessary to measure the density of the solution, which is an extremely difficult process when dealing with supersaturated solutions. It is immaterial whether equal volumes of solution are used in the different experiments or not.

FIG. 1

The viscometer and the other apparatus used are shown in Fig. 1. 'A' is a test tube which is fitted with a rubber stopper through which passes a viscometer 'B', and two other tubes. The bulb of the viscometer is filled with the solution in A by the application of suction. The suction to be exerted depends on the difference of water level in the aspirator 'E' and the jar placed underneath; a water manometer 'M' attached to this reads the pressure applied for sucking the solution to the top of the bulb. All the adjustments are made by stop-cocks, well lubricated with good vacuum grease which facilitates an accurate adjustment of the pressure. It was found by working with saturated solutions that a pressure of 25 cm. was necessary for a decent interval of time.

The U-tubes 'C' and 'D' are connected with a three-way tap, T_2 , which puts one or the other of the U-tube into communication with the dust-free air contained in the aspirator 'F'. The air from outside has to pass through the spiral 'S', coated inside with grease, which removes the dust particles suspended in the air which further comes into contact with spray fitted at the mouth of the aspirator F. Thus every precaution is taken to see that the air, coming into contact with the supersaturated solution, is free from dust, which, if present, will bring about crystallisation even in the "metastable" region.

It is necessary to pass a current of dust-free air through the whole apparatus several times before the commencement of each experiment. After closing the tap T_2 , water is made to flow into the aspirator 'G'. The air in the upper part of the aspirator is forced out, and after being washed in the Woulfe's bottle 'H', is made to circulate through the whole apparatus and then finally ejected into the aspirator F. Purified air from the aspirator F passes into G when the water is removed from the bottom. Thus dust-free air is kept circulated through the apparatus from time to time.

When the solution is to be sucked up into the bulb of the viscometer, the tap T_2 is turned so as to put the U-tube D into communication with the air in the aspirator F, and suction applied by opening the tap T_1 . When the bulb is to be emptied, tap T_1 is closed, and both the U-tubes are simultaneously put into communication with the air in the aspirator F. These two taps (T_1 and T_2) are fixed on the ground level very near the thermostat so that easy manipulation is ensured. Both the U-tubes contain a small quantity of water which replaces any loss due to evaporation of the solvent from the surface of the solution (a precaution necessary when dealing with supersaturated solutions).

The thermostat used was electrically heated and regulated by a toluene-mercury regulator. The temperature was measured by means of a thermometer reading up to 0.1°C .

In carrying out an experiment, the substance to be examined was weighed out carefully (the amount depending on its solubility) into a small conical flask and a measured quantity of water was added to make it saturated at the required temperature. The solubility data from the International Critical Tables (Vol. II, 1928) and Chemical Engineer's Hand book (1950) were taken. The mouth of the flask was closed with a rubber stopper. The flask was heated in boiling water till all the solid had gone into solution. The solutions were always kept at least 5° above the temperature of saturation. The rubber stopper was then removed from the flask and the solution was carefully transferred to the bottom of the tube carrying the viscometer as quickly as possible. The rubber stopper was replaced and the whole apparatus was placed in the thermostat. After adjusting the viscometer in a vertical position, the solution was allowed to attain the constant temperature of the thermostat for about 30 minutes. The times taken for the ascent and descent of the solution were measured by means of a stop-watch reading $1/100$ of a second, several readings having been taken for each temperature. The next reading was taken after cooling the thermostat, a degree or so below the original temperature. This process was repeated till a shower of crystals throughout the solution was noticed, as described by Miers and Issac (*loc. cit.*). Every time

a new experiment was started, the viscometer was cleaned and dried before use. From saturated solutions at different temperatures the viscosity at different temperature of supersaturation was noted.

The data are presented graphically in Figs. 2 and 3. It is seen that for substances like KCl , KBr , KI and K_2SO_4 (Fig. 2), temperature coefficient of solubility of which is constant throughout the ranges of temperature, the graph is a straight line; which shows that viscosity (η) varies linearly with temperature (T) of supersaturated solution for these substances. For other substances like $K_2Cr_2O_7$, $Ba(NO_3)_2$, NH_4Cl , NH_4Br and $KClO_3$, the straight line graph is not obtained (Fig. 3); their temperature coefficient of solubility is not also constant. η and T relation may be exponential in these cases.

The authors desire to express their thanks to Dr. B. S. Srikantan for the interest that he has been taking in this investigation.

Thanks are due to the Government of India for a research grant towards the cost of the apparatus and viscometers.